

TRAINING SWIMMING TECHNIQUES FOR YOUNG ATHLETES

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Annotation: Due to its sports, applied, health and general developmental significance, swimming is one of the main sections of social programs for health improvement and physical education of various age groups of the population. In the system of physical education, swimming is presented as a mass means of versatile physical development and a vital skill that every citizen should master from childhood, as well as a mass means of health improvement, hardening, and active recreation of the population; means of professional application.

Key words: swimming, young swimmers, teaching methods, swimming technique, stages of training athletes.

Introduction. The main task of modernizing the system of physical education and sports training is the introduction of pedagogical technologies into the educational and training process, taking into account the individual characteristics of athletes involved [1, 2]. In the theory and methodology of physical education and sports training, the problem of organizing a differentiated approach is recognized as relevant and requires more in-depth study. Many aspects of this issue have been scientifically developed, thanks to which the signs underlying it have become obvious: the state of health and the level of physical development, the level of physical fitness, the degree of biological maturity, the properties of the nervous system and temperament [3, 5, 7]. Although often in practice, a differentiated approach is based only on intuition, the pedagogical experience of the trainer and is

limited to a one-time episodic impact on students, not representing a holistic system of working with different groups of students [4, 6, 8].

According to some researchers, loads that do not correspond to the adaptive capabilities of children's bodies already at primary school age lead to a deterioration in children's health and negatively affect the overstrain of the body, most often the cardiovascular system (juvenile hypertension, myocardial conduction disorders) [9, 10, 11, 12]. Therefore, in the educational and training process, it is important to take into account the anatomical and physiological characteristics of the child's growing body, as well as age-related characteristics of the development of motor qualities. From an anatomical and physiological point of view, primary school age is often considered as relatively calm (in comparison, for example, with adolescence). But this does not mean that we are spared the need to carefully take into account the physiological features of this age, which are also influenced by the individual characteristics of each child [13, 14].

An analysis of the research of many authors on the problem of the training process at the stages of sports improvement and higher sports mastery has shown that an individual approach is mainly used in the training process of highly qualified athletes and concerns, first of all, the individual characteristics of the technique of performing exercises, work and rest modes, and managing sports motives. activities [12, 14].

According to the researchers, an attempt was made to create individually oriented programs that primarily take into account the initial level of condition and the predicted potential of the athlete.

At the same time, at the stage of initial training of athletes, it is not possible to fully use the individual approach for organizational and methodological reasons (large number of training groups, heterogeneous contingent, strict regulation and unification of methods and forms of the educational and training process, insufficient elaboration of individualization technology). Some researchers suggest using a differentiated approach to building the training process, taking into account

the characteristics characteristic of different groups of young athletes, which are important for the application of training loads, teaching technical and tactical actions, and participation in competitions [5, 7].

The use of a differentiated approach at the stage of initial training of athletes requires more detailed consideration, study and generalization, since physical activity in sports schools significantly exceeds the load in school lessons and requires more detailed development and systematization of the training process. Thus, in our opinion, the need to develop targeted programs for differentiated training of young athletes is obvious. Work in this direction should begin at primary school age: during this period, motor abilities are formed and the foundations of the body's functional reserves are laid [15, 16].

Despite the efforts of many researchers to find the most effective means that purposefully influence the formation of movement technique in the process of learning to swim, the desired result has not yet been achieved, since the learning process takes a long time and a large percentage of children have not mastered the skill of swimming. This is especially true for preschool children, since during this period the most intensive formation of knowledge, skills, and abilities occurs. Associated with this age is a global mental neoplasm - arbitrariness of mental processes and behavior, manifested in the ability to control one's mental and motor activity.

The structure of the musculoskeletal system of children of primary school age provides them with a fairly high level of development of flexibility, coordination abilities, and good buoyancy, which makes it easier to learn movements to develop swimming techniques. Rational swimming technique is the main component of the initial training stage, ensuring the achievement of high sports results in the future. It is at this stage of preparation that children form the foundations of rational swimming techniques, creating a solid foundation for future technical mastery.

The psychological characteristics of students of primary school age determine the need for various forms and methods of organizing classes against the backdrop

of positive emotions. The main means of improving swimming technique are the following groups of physical exercises:

- general developmental, special and simulation exercises on land;
- exercises to improve the starting jump technique;
- games and entertainment on the water;
- exercises to improve the technique of sports swimming methods;
- exercises for studying and improving the technique of performing turns.

Improving sports swimming techniques is carried out in the following main areas:

- achieving coordination of movements of the arms, legs, torso and breathing;
- developing the skill of deep and rhythmic breathing;
- reducing water resistance to the movement of the swimmer's body;
- increasing the traction forces of hand strokes;
- determination of the optimal tempo of movements at a distance with good progress from hand strokes.

Conclusions. A study was conducted of the level of technical preparedness of the experimental group during the use of a set of exercises. The experiment we conducted made it possible to identify the effectiveness of using the proposed set of exercises. Girls and boys in the experimental group showed a significantly higher level of technical readiness compared to the beginning of the experiment. Therefore, we can conclude that the developed set of exercises makes it possible to improve the swimming technique of young athletes at the initial training stage of the 2nd year of study.

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